

Anion-exchange Selectivity in Water-DMF Medium

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Manuscript received 8 March 1982, revised 1 December 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

The exchange behaviour of simple monovalent anions ClO_4^- , I^- , NO_3^- and Cl^- as a function of the water-DMF solvent compositions 0, 20, 40, 70 and 80% (w/w) at 303 ± 0.1 K on strong base anion-exchanger, such as Dowex 1-X4 was carried out. The results are discussed in terms of the models proposed by Diamond and Reichenberg.

THE importance of ion-exchange processes in modern separation techniques arises because of the selectivity exhibited by ion-exchangers. Ion-exchange equilibria in water-DMF mixed medium were investigated by using the chloride form of the resin as the reference, and the monovalent ions (ClO_4^- , I^- , NO_3^-) as the counter-ions. All the exchange experiments were carried out at 303 ± 0.1 K on strong base anion-exchanger, such as Dowex 1-X4. The results are discussed in terms of models of Diamond¹ and Reichenberg².

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (AnalaR) was distilled at 58° under reduced pressure. Solvent mixtures containing 20, 40, 70 and 80% (w/w) DMF in water were prepared. Solutions in the mixed solvents were prepared by dissolving directly the solid salts in solvent mixtures. All the weighings were done to a precision of 0.2 mg.

Dowex 1-X4 (A.R. grade, J. T. Baker Chemical Co., 50-100 mesh beads) were conditioned, converted into the chloride form, air-dried and stored. The moisture content and capacity of these resin beads were found to be 20 ± 1 wt% and 3.2 meq g^{-1} of resin, respectively.

Determination of selectivity coefficient: Air-dried resin beads (250 mg) were weighed into 100 ml stoppered flasks. Standard electrolyte solutions of Cl^- and of other anions of 0.05 M strength were added to the resin in varying proportions to give a total volume of 30 ml and a total ionic strength 0.05 M. The flasks were tightly stoppered and the equilibration of the exchange reaction mixture was carried out by shaking them for 8 h in a thermostated water-bath at 303.0 ± 0.1 K, with a reciprocal type of mechanical shaker.

After equilibration, a known aliquot from the external solution phase was pipetted out for the estimation of ions. In the case of ClO_4^- - Cl^- system, the chloride content of the aliquot was

estimated by Volhard's method. In the case of I^- - Cl^- system, the ^{131}I tracer (carrier free in Na_2SO_4) was added initially. After equilibration, two 5.0 ml aliquots of solutions were carefully pipetted out and γ -ray activity was measured using a well-type NaI (Tl) scintillation counter with a single channel analyser. Samples of the stock solution were also counted to give the initial tracer activity. After correction for the background count, the amount of iodide in the external solution phase was calculated.

From the above data and the known total capacity of the exchanger the equilibrium concentration of both the counter-ions in the two phases were calculated. The selectivity coefficient for an anion under the given condition (at one loading) is calculated as exemplified below for the exchange.

$$K_{\text{cCl}^-}^{\text{B}^-} = \frac{\bar{N} \text{RB} \cdot \text{Cl}^-}{\bar{N} \text{RCl} \cdot \text{B}^-}$$

where, $K_{\text{cCl}^-}^{\text{B}^-}$ = selectivity coefficient, $\bar{N} \text{RB}$ and $\bar{N} \text{RCl}$ are the equivalent fractions of B^- and Cl^- ions in the resin phase. The activity coefficients are omitted as the exchange reactions are carried out in a dilute solution of 0.05 M strength.

The $K_{\text{cCl}^-}^{\text{B}^-}$ values at different loadings were evaluated using a computer programme for the least-square fitting for a polynomial of degree two on a BESM-6 computer at B.A.R.C., Bombay.

The $K_{\text{cCl}^-}^{\text{B}^-}$ values, obtained for NO_3^- - Cl^- , I^- - Cl^- and ClO_4^- - Cl^- systems on Dowex 1-X4 in DMF (0, 20, 40, 70 and 80%, w/w)-water media, were plotted against the corresponding loading $\bar{N} \text{R}$ values and are summarised in Fig. 1. The averaged selectivity coefficient $K_{\text{cCl}^-}^{\text{B}^-}$ as a function of solvent composition for all the three systems are grouped in Fig. 2.

Results and Discussion

The order of selectivity on strong base-exchanger Dowex 1-X4 in the aqueous medium is, $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^-$

Fig. 1. Selectivity coefficient of I^- as a function of resin phase composition on Dowex 1-X4; DMF(w/w): (O) 0, (Δ) 2, (\square) 40, (\times) 70 and (\bullet) 80%.

Fig. 2. Selectivity coefficients of ClO_4^- , I^- and NO_3^- as a function of DMF-water composition on Dowex 1-X4: (O) ClO_4^- , (\times) I^- and (\bullet) NO_3^- .

$>NO_3^- > Cl^-$. The results of the present investigation in aqueous medium support the Diamond's model. Among the counter-ions studied, the Cl^- ion in water at the dilution employed exhibits the highest hydration energy^a (Table 1).

According to Diamond's model, the chloride ion would be in the external aqueous phase and this is in agreement with the observed selectivity order. Selectivity of larger monovalent anion, such as ClO_4^- is further enhanced by the entropy effect⁴. This is in agreement with our present experiment where average selectivity coefficient $K_{a,Cl^-}^{B^-}$ for ClO_4^- is larger than that for NO_3^- (Table 2).

A comparison of the reported free energy values for exchange studies between pairs of anions on Dowex 1-X4 in aqueous medium by different investigators is very good; for $ClO_4^- - Cl^-$ exchange (Table 3) this value ranges from 2.29 to 2.69 kcal mol⁻¹ with most of the values lying in close agreement. This clearly suggests that in the anion-exchange selectivity process, there are other types of contributory interaction-effects, besides the difference in the hydration energy.

The observed phenomenon in water-DMF medium can be explained by the effects of the aprotic organic solvent on the structure of water, and by the preferential ion solvation effects.

The actual solvent composition at equilibrium may not be the same as the initial composition because of the preferential absorption of water by the strong base resin. Since it requires more work to place charges in the aqueous DMF mixture than in the original aqueous system, there is an increase in the electrostatic free energy of the system when water molecules are replaced by organic molecules⁶. Upon the addition of DMF the resin will suffer a much larger electrostatic free energy increase than the external phase, because it has a high concentration of charge while the external solution is electro-neutral. Water and DMF distribute in such a way as to minimise this increase in the free energy for the whole system and clearly this can best be done if the solvent that can provide the best electrostatic solvation moves preferentially into the resin phase. As the concentration of DMF is increased, however,

TABLE 1— $\Delta G_{i(h)}^\circ$ OF MONOVALENT ANIONS AND $\Delta G_{Cl^-}^{B^-}$ VALUES FOR EXCHANGES ON STRONG BASE EXCHANGERS

Temp. = 303.0 K			
Anion	Free energy of hydration ($-\Delta G_{i(h)}^\circ$) kcal mol ⁻¹	Difference between free energies of hydration ($\Delta G_{Cl^-}^{B^-}(h) - \Delta G_{B^-}^\circ(h)$) kcal mol ⁻¹	Standard free energy of an ion-exchange reaction ($\Delta G_{Cl^-}^{B^-}$) kcal mol ⁻¹
Cl^-	79	0.0	0.00
Br^-	72	-7	-0.57 ^a
I^-	64	-15	-1.51 ^a
NO_3^-	69	-10	-0.75 ^a
ClO_4^-	50	-29	-2.35 ^a
			-1.54 ^c -1.26 ^d 1.89 ^b
			-0.72 ^c -2.29 ^d 0.46 ^b
			-2.69 ^c -2.39 ^d 2.39 ^b

^a K. Gartner, *Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1963, 223, 132. ^b Present work. ^c R. K. Bhat, Ph. D. Thesis, Karnatak University, 1970. ^d C. S. Narke and K. S. Math, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1979, 14, 55. ^e Ref. 5.

TABLE 2—AVERAGED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENT K_{aCl}^{B-} IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM ON DOWEX 1-X4

Total ionic strength = 0.05 M

$\log K_{aCl}^{NO_3^-}$	0.62
$\log K_{aCl}^{I^-}$	1.86
$\log K_{aCl}^{ClO_4^-}$	1.67

the ion-dipole interactions between the bigger anions and DMF molecules will increase and thus resulting in decrease for the preference for the bigger anions by the resin.

Increase of DMF concentration in the external solution generally decreased the averaged selectivity coefficient K_{aCl}^{B-} for the pairs of ions investigated, $ClO_4^- - Cl^-$, $I^- - Cl^-$ and $NO_3^- - Cl^-$ (Fig. 2). Anions, preferred by the resin in aqueous solution, become less preferred in water-DMF mixed solvent and reversals in selectivity are generally observed. Due to the absence of acidic hydrogen capable of hydrogen bonding, water-DMF mixed solvent medium will be gradually become a poorer solvating agent for anions as the concentration of DMF is increased. In addition, the dipolar aprotic DMF acts as a base towards the water molecules, competing with anions for hydrogen bonding to water and breaking up the hydrogen bonded water structure.

The preferential selectivity of ClO_4^- on the strong base resin in water-DMF medium should decrease rapidly with an increase in DMF content, both because of the reduction of superiority in the external solution for solvating Cl^- ions. The results of the present investigation support this contention (Fig. 1). The bigger ions preferred by the resin become less preferred in the water-DMF solutions. In all the cases at 80% water-DMF composition selectivity reversals are observed (Fig. 2).

In the theory of anion-exchange selectivity outlined by Reichenberg³ the counter ion must lose some molecules of solvation in order to become associated or influenced by the fixed ionic group. Selectivity, therefore, is governed by the energy of solvation; consequently, the system attains stability by pushing anion with a low hydration energy from the resin to the external solution phase where hydration can be more extensive. The selectivity of anions in the present work is in agreement with the data of free energy of hydration (Table 3).

TABLE 3—AVERAGED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS K_{aCl}^{B-} IN DMF-WATER MEDIUM ON DOWEX 1-X4

Temp. = 303 ± 0.1 K

Exchanging ion	$\log K_{aCl}^{B-}$ at % (w/w) DMF			
	20	40	70	80
NO_3^-	-0.89	-0.97	-0.77	-1.71
I^-	1.11	0.69	0.98	-0.46
ClO_4^-	1.04	0.81	0.44	-0.89

Thus, the results of the present investigation on ClO_4^- , I^- , NO_3^- and Cl^- in water and water-DMF medium support the models proposed by Diamond¹ and Reichenberg³. In all the cases selectivity coefficients vary significantly with the resin phase composition both in aqueous and water-DMF mixed solvent medium. The selectivity coefficient for the exchange of I^- vs Cl^- on Dowex 1-X4 as a function of loading is shown in Fig. 1. The nature of the curves is generally parabolic, and shows that selectivity coefficient $K_{aCl}^{I^-}$ decrease steadily with increasing DMF concentration in the external solution. Upto 40% water-DMF composition the selectivity, $I^- > Cl^-$ is still maintained. In 80% water-DMF composition the chloride becomes a preferred ion and selectivity reversal, $Cl^- > I^-$ is observed.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. M. S. Chandrashekharaiah for his keen interest and valuable advice. Thanks are due to Drs. M. Sankar Das, M. Sundaresan, B. L. Jangida of B.A.R.C., Bombay, for encouragement. The authors are also indebted to Prof. E. S. Jayadevappa of Chemistry Department, Karnataka University, for interest. One of the authors (S.P.K.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for a fellowship.

References

1. R. M. DIAMOND, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 67, 2818.
2. D. REICHENBERG in "Ion Exchange", ed. J. A. MARINSKY, Dekker, New York, 1966, Vol. 1, Chap. 7.
3. G. E. BOYD in "Analytical Calorimetry", eds. R. S. PORTER and J. P. JOHNSON, Plenum, New York, 1968, p. 141.
4. R. M. DIAMOND and D. O. WHITNEY in "Ion Exchange", ed. J. A. MARINSKY, Dekker, New York, 1966, Vol. 1, Chap. 8.
5. O. H. JENSEN, A. PATRIDGE, T. KENJO, J. BUTCHER and R. M. DIAMOND, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, 76, 1010.